

Readme

Defining Security Debt: A Case Study Based On Practice

The following files are uploaded:

- Interview guide
- Coding scheme
- Security debt and security vulnerability relationship groups
- Technical debt description groups

The “**Interview guide**” file provides an overview of the interview guide followed in the 26 semi-structured interviews. The first part of the interviews (see “Consent” rows) was allocated to describing the purpose of the research and collecting consent to proceed. As part of the second section of the interviews (see “Introduction” row), the interviewer asked introductory questions to understand the background such as the duration of the project. The main part of the interviews were allocated to questions on technical debt and security debt (see “TD” and “SD” rows). Lastly, the interviews were wrapped up (see “Conclusion” row).

The “**Coding scheme**” file describes the codes used to analyze the collected data. Each of the codes are briefly described and mapped to the research questions/areas where the data were used. The “# of occurrences” column shows how many times the codes were used.

The “**Security debt and security vulnerability relationship groups**” file contains groups that explain the relation between security debt and security vulnerabilities. These groups were created based on similarities in the respondents’ answers. The respondents can be in more than one group if they have several ways of viewing the relation between security debt and security vulnerabilities.

The “**Technical debt description groups**” file lists the groups of technical debt descriptions (characteristics) created based on the respondents’ answers. The respondents can be in more than one group if they have several ways of describing TD. Three of the characteristics are mentioned by the respondents to apply to security debt as well. This is shown as “Characteristics also mentioned for SD?”=Yes in the table.